

DYNAMIC EFFECTS OF EUROPEAN UNION AND CUSTOMS UNION PRACTICES ON TURKEY AND BULGARIA

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ДИНАМИЧНИ ЕФЕКТИ ОТ ЕВРОПЕЙСКИТЕ ПРАКТИКИ НА МИТНИЧЕСКИЯ СЪЮЗ ВЪРХУ ТУРЦИЯ И БЪЛГАРИЯ

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Abstract

Joining a customs union such as the European Union brings a lot of benefits to its members in both short and long term and is followed by an array of static and dynamic effects on the economy. The aim of the current paper is the so-called dynamic economic effects of the customs union practices related to Turkey and Bulgaria to be examined.

Key words: customs union, dynamic effects, competitiveness, economies of scale, external economies, technological advancement

Резюме

Присъединяването към един митнически съюз, както е Европейския съюз принася редица ползи на неговите членове както в краткосрочен, така и в дългосрочен план, следвани от редица статични и динамични ефекти върху икономиките на отделните държави.

Цел на статията е да бъдат разгледани т. нар. динамични икономически ефекти за Турция и България от присъединяването им към митническия съюз в рамките на ЕС.

Ключови думи: митнически съюз, динамични ефекти, конкурентоспособност, икономии от мащаба, външни икономии, технологичен напредък

1. Introduction

Countries aspire to become members of the European Union (EU), an important force in our day, to benefit from the advantages it brings. Bulgaria has become a member of EU in

this sense in 2007. However, Turkey could not become a member since 1950's. Besides, Turkey has entered into customs union process with EU. Customs union has been put into effect in 1996. As a result, EU customs union has introduced some effects on Bulgaria and Turkey. These will be discussed below.

2. Effects of European Union and Customs Union practices on Turkey and Bulgaria

By removal of protectionism according to Customs Unions Theory, short term static and long term dynamic effects occur in the member states economies. Customs unions are expected to increase the commerce between states in the short term. While in the long term, increased competitiveness and restructuring effects are in question. The first of these effects occurs at the moment of realizing the union and is easy to calculate. However, long term effects mostly can't be calculated due to requiring dynamic analysis and external conditions can change. However, the benefits expected from customs union are from more effective distribution of resources within the framework of long term restructuring effects rather than short term effects (Kızıltan, Ersungur & Polat, 2008: 84).

With the Customs Union (CU) agreement Turkey made with EU, the restrictions for the commerce in the Union have been removed significantly and a common customs tariff was started to be used against third countries. As a result, static and dynamic effects of CU on Turkey's economy have been observed (Kayihan & Yıldız, 2009: 729).

In the current paper, the dynamic effects of EU-Customs Union practices will be examined, specific to Turkey and Bulgaria. Dynamic effects will be explained as competitiveness, economies of scale, external economies, technological advancement and investment promotions.

The dynamic effects of customs unions are structural changes in the economy and sectors caused by market integration in middle and long term. It is stronger and more persistent with these qualities compared to static effects (Atmaca, 1995: 26).

Customs Union has a meaning of transition to big market from small market. For this reason, economies can obtain the advantages of the big market. The advantages brought by the big market are called dynamic effects of Customs Union. Dynamic effects of the Customs Union means the occurring of internal and external economies as a result of market growth, use of more advanced technology, increase in expertise and decreasing, even disappearing of uncertainty for investors (Hatipler, 2012: 5).

2.1. Effects of Competition

The first one to suggest effects of competition of customs union was the economist Scitovsky. Later, Balassa has contributed to this effect in 1961. Balassa has explained that customs unions would decrease the market power of national monopolies or cause price or non-price competition to increase by removing means of agreement under oligopolistic market structure. Both economists have claimed that because of the foreign companies' fear of entering into the market, local companies would lower their prices to competitive level. But, there are also those who defend that local monopolies would gain power and international cartels would emerge by establishment of customs unions. According to them, economic integrations (such as EU) contribute to the monopolistic capitalism to take root. Tinbergen (1954) does not accept that customs unions increase the level of monopolization directly. However, he defends that instead of customs union's indirect competition effects, direct

measures to be taken for the purpose of increasing competition are more effective (Karluk, 2009: 187).

The competition effect brought into open on the member state economies can be examined by dividing into two. These are the effect on the competition environment in the domestic market of member state and the effect on the competitive capacity of member state in international markets. According to customs union theory, one of the most important benefits provided by customs union membership is brought into open on competition environment. As a result of removal of customs tariffs and practicing of common customs tariff with customs union, while the entrance conditions to the market of member state are getting better, member state's entrance conditions to union market also get better. Liberalized entrance conditions to market is sufficient to increase the competition and the increased competition in domestic markets forces the companies not working efficiently to leave their current sector and shifts them to the areas they are efficient. But, the theory does not have a certain projection on how the international market competitive capacity of the state that joins the union will be affected from this integration. For example, while the polarization theory, in the example of customs union between developed countries and a developing county, have the prediction that a developing country's competitive capacity will have negative impact, the competitive capacity of the developing country is predicted to increase in at least capital-intensive goods and advanced technology products via trade with increased catching paradigm (Vergil & Yıldırım, 2006: 1-2).

Considering the changes made to Turkish legislation in competition area post-Customs Union, it can be said that Customs Union, increasing the production quality of Turkish industry in national and international level by taking maximum benefit of end user as a prerequisite, forms a framework to necessary works towards increasing competitive capacity. Besides, to relevant institutions of public level and Turkish industrialist, it can be pointed out that it gains momentum for immediately starting works towards this direction and cause a change of mindset towards production quality and consumer satisfaction being the key determinants of profit (Çak & Çak, 2007: 40).

As a result of Customs Union Agreement, while Turkey was applying European Union's common customs union tariffs to third worlds, Far East Countries such as China and India, competitors of Turkey in many sectors, use the advantage of being exempt from this tariff and increased their competitive capacity against Turkey (Eşiyok, 2012).

In the study conducted by Vergil and Yıldırım, "Effects of EU-Turkey Customs Union over Turkey's Competitive Capacity", the findings are as follows: While reaching the results of Turkey-EU customs union's positive effect on competitive capacity for Turkey's both in advanced technology products and in hard to copy products accordingly with catching paradigm, also the results of the negative effects on the competitive capacity for capital-intensive products and intermediate technology products that support polarization theory predictions (Vergil & Yıl, 2006: 16).

In the study of Türker's "Turkey's Foreign Trade Competitive Capacity Post-Customs Union"; 15 countries which were full members of EU before 1996 were compared to Turkey. During customs union process, the change in Turkey's competitive capacity was compared to the changes in the competitive capacities of these countries in the same period. In this comparison, the competitive capacities of sectors included in the Standard Industrial Product

Grouping were measured by using Revealed Comparative Advantages method. The effect of the customs union to Turkey's competitive capacity, while providing a lower competitive capacity to some product groups, is generally considered as not increasing the competitive capacity of Turkey. Because, a lower competitive capacity indexes emerged in many sectors after the customs union (Türker, 2009: 299-300).

Customs union not contributing significantly to Turkey's competitive capacity means Turkey is gradually becoming an open market. In all the sectors losing their competitive capacity, more production decrease will happen and correspondingly, income and employment will also decrease. For this reason, Turkey should hasten the efforts to increase its competitive capacity. In this context, R&D, product development, innovation processes should be prioritized (Türker, 2009: 300).

2.2. Economies of Scale Effect

CU will provide the manufacturers to produce for a bigger market. In other words, CU's making the locally produced goods entering union markets easier will cause local companies to use their unutilized capacities or go for capacity increase. Two advantages of economies of scale can be mentioned. The first is the decreases caused by growing company and industry scale. The second is expected on product range. Due to market being narrow, product range will also be small. While the CU is enlarging market volume, companies will increase their scale and product ranges. Thus, production efficiency increases will occur (Yıldırım & Dura, 2007: 147).

2.3. External Economies Effect

External economy can be defined as the positive or negative effects made by a manufacturer or a consumer on the production or consumption function of another manufacturer or a consumer. Suggested for the first time by A. Marshall, the external economies concept is used to explain increased returns while examining the production costs of companies in the industry (Çak & Çak, 2007: 17).

Depending on changes in supply and demand conditions, external economies can be gathered under two groups. In external economies depending on supply conditions, a company lowers its costs due to progress in the production technique and provides the manufactured product to other companies in lower price. In external economies depending on demand conditions, production increase in the first industry causes the income-demand spiral. This effect implies that the sectors not included in the customs union may also be affected by this integration in the customs union where some sectors are included. Efficiency and product quality of some companies increase as a result of economies of scale, competition and technological advancement effects. Other companies receiving input from these companies obtain cheaper and more quality inputs. Thus, the general performance of the economy increases (Temiz, 2009: 126).

2.4. Technological Advancement Effect

By establishment of Customs Union, technological advancement in economy is promoted. According to Scitovsky (1958), because monopolistic and oligopolistic companies avoid uncertainty, they would want maintain their status in the customs union and take advantage of new inventions. Increase of competition will increase the efforts of monopolistic and oligopolistic companies on making new inventions and trigger technological advancement. Also, as a result of increase in competition, research and development expenses

will be increased for development of new products and production techniques. Balassa (1961), points out that large scale companies make more research and development expenses, so the increase in scale of companies after the customs union will also cause an increase in research and development expenses. Also, customs union provides spreading of technological knowledge and technological processes developed in other member states by allowing manufacturers to meet new products (Karluk, 2009: 287).

It was expected of Turkey to develop in technological way by entering an industrialized market Post-CU. However, in 2005, it is observed that Turkey still maintains its labor-intensive structure. Because, the presence of cheap and unrecorded employment in SMSE's which realizes a large portion of production and weakness of financial structures prevents use of high-cost technology. A large portion of exportation consists of textile and apparel products and food products where labor-intensive and relatively old technology is used (Gökdemir & Karaman, 2008: 289).

A significant reason for Turkey's foreign trade deficit is due to the fact that we haven't reached a technologically required level. The high technology parts of a television or an automobile manufactured in Turkey and exported to EU countries are imported from abroad, especially Far East and Asia countries. This, in turn, causes the decrease in additional value of exportation and pumps importation numbers. Most important reasons for falling behind in technology are not giving due consideration to R&D investment and activities in public, universities and private sector and seeing R&D investments as "unnecessary" and "superfluous" expenses. There may not be anything to do in terms of importing materials like petroleum and natural gas. But keeping up with the times in technology is possible by cooperation and investment of government, universities and private sector. It is very difficult to deal with countries like China and India where the cheap labor is present in labor-intensive sectors. The labor in these countries is quite cheap and working conditions are quite hard. The only way to completely close the foreign trade deficit of our country is giving due importance to R&D and technology and decreasing importing of technological intermediate products as much as possible (Antalya EU Information Center).

2.5. Incentive Effect of Investments

It is expected for the increase to happen in foreign capital investments to come from the countries outside the union due to CU. The reasons of countries outside the union investing to countries forming the union can be listed as giving assurance to investors on tariffs not be increased again in the CU, the trade deviation caused by customs unions decreasing the importation made by union members from outside world, trade increase between union members attracting the investors who are outside the union, increase of economic stability and efficiency within union, demand to use the production factors within union encouraging foreign investors by increasing of employment, income and capital marginal effectiveness (Temiz, 2009: 127).

Turkey is an attractive investment spot for union member states as well as third countries due to its young, dynamic and unsaturated market and geographical location which provides connection with Middle East, Black sea and Asia (Seymen, 71).

It is expected for the investments to increase in conjunction with expansion of market volume and source effectiveness. Foreign capital, which is expected to enter into the country post-Customs Union, plays a huge role. However, not being able to establish a stable market

organization will cause the foreign capital which is always looking for a safe environment to remain limited post-Customs Union despite cheap labor (Yüceol, 1999: 142).

It had been presumed that Turkey's entrance to CU will remove some political and economic uncertainties, increase the environment of trust and thus, a substantial increase in foreign capital investments. Following Turkey's entrance to CU, an increase in foreign capital inflow has happened. However, a large portion of this was in the form of short term capital, which is called hot money. Long term capital movements are towards privatization and purchasing of current businesses rather than new investments. The contribution of short term capital to the economy of the country is much-discussed. Because, there are serious findings towards short term capital movements causing instability over the economies of the countries and increasing economic crisis in the process of globalization. Thus, big economic crises have happened in Turkey in 1999, 2001 and 2008 post-CU. Consequently, capital inflow has happened on a limited scale (Kayıhan & Yıldız, 2009: 736).

The expectations concerning the increase of foreign capital investments post-CU was not realized. This situation is mainly resulting from Turkey's inability to provide safe market conditions to investors, which itself couldn't ensure an economic and political stability (Seymen, 71).

To compare Turkey and Bulgaria, it is useful to look into Bulgaria's investment environment. In this respect, elements positively and negatively affecting investments in Bulgaria will be examined.

Elements positively affecting the investments are the following (www.ekonomi.gov.tr, 2015: 75):

- Bulgaria is a member of EU, NATO and WTO.
- Because Bulgaria is a member of EU, products, services, capital and people have the right to free circulation.
- Bulgaria has a role of "bridge" or "gateway" in products of Turkish companies into EU markets.
- Turkish companies can take advantage of EU funds in Bulgaria.
- The rate of exchange for Bulgarian Leva (BGN) Euro is 1,95583.
- Bulgaria is in an important logistic location as it is located in the middle of Balkans and five Pan-European corridors pass over it. The country has four airports, two main seaports and many ports over river Danube.
- The lowest corporate tax in the European Union is in Bulgaria: 10%. The regions with highest unemployment rate are exempt from corporate tax. Income tax is also at 10%.
- VAT exemption for two years for the equipment importation in investment projects over 5 million Euros and creating employment to 50 people.
- Period of redemption for computer and new manufacturing machines is 2 years.
- Labor cost in Bulgaria is one of the lowest in Middle and Eastern Europe countries.
- Electricity price is significantly lower than Europe average.
- 53 universities and 541 high schools are active in Bulgaria. Each year, 60 thousand students graduate from the universities in the country. University graduates constitute 25% of the population.

- 60% of the population at prime-age (25-64) knows at least one foreign language, 80% are at high school and above education level. 7% of the active workforce is engineers.
- 94% of the schools have access to internet.

The factors negatively affecting the investments and business making environment in Bulgaria are listed as high unemployment rate, low labor productivity, insufficiency in attracting competent workforce, young population migrating to European countries, corruption, bureaucratic inefficiency, financial difficulties, political instability in the recent years, limited R&D activities, problems in ruling, no transparency in government policies, decrease of trust to politicians (www.ekonomi.gov.tr, 2015: 76).

3. Conclusion

When considering the effects for a certain economy from entering a customs union, in particular the EU, dynamic effects for it need to be carefully considered and analyzed. The comparison between the effects for Turkey and Bulgaria shows a number of specificities, as long as manifestations are concerned. This is logical, since the two countries have significant differences in terms of structure of the economies, size and demand and supply patterns. Yet there are certain similarities which come to prove that there are specific repeating patterns for all economies entering CU.

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